

IMPROVING THE APPLICATION OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES TO THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS OF UROLOGY

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Abstract. *This article covers the problems and relevance of improving the application of innovative technologies to the educational process of Urology for students of the urology direction of the medical institution.*

Keywords: *frame, profession, training, education, process, improvement, medical high school, students, urology science, innovation, simulation, technology.*

Information on the integration of modern information communication technologies into the field of education and medicine, current problems in the social sphere and news are analyzed by educators and transmitted to the minds of those who receive education, relying on professional skills. The acceleration of the development process requires various approaches that should be applied not only in the professional activities of pedagogical personnel, but also in the professional activities of specialists working in the field of Medicine[1].

Professor of Medical Sciences Selchuk Yuzhel says about urological diseases. "According to statistics, prostate adenoma is the most common disease, occurring in every sixth man. In the "risk group" - people over 50 years old. The reason for the development of prostate adenoma is hormonal disorders that are observed in the body of men as they age. Subsequent cases of kidney cancer, gallbladder cancer, inability to hold the bladder, erectile dysfunction (impotence) may be noted. Children, on the other hand, are often disturbed by kidney disease and infections in the pubic tract"[3] he says.

As with other areas of reproductive health, it is necessary that the parents of children, especially boys, are very attentive to care about childhood, to identify or treat the disease at the initial stage of development. If the child has difficulty getting involved or, on the contrary, often gets out there, this can be enough grounds to see a doctor. If the child has noticed that the way out of the forehead is not in its place, it is necessary to consult a specialist. When bathing a child, it is necessary to pay attention to whether his testicles have completely fallen or not. If one of the testicles has not completely fallen off, this can lead to infertility in the future. If the testicles are trapped inside the body, it leads to the development of cancer. It should also be said that if the child has a kidney or a stone in the gallbladder, he will begin to complain of abdominal pain.

In children, the pain in the formation of a stone is different from that of an adult, and its heat can come out and press tremors. In case of such signs, it is necessary to extend the referral to the doctors of practice. In addition, if the disease is Hereditary, the chances of its development will be higher.

The above signs for the health of young parents or children caregivers need to see a doctor and undergo an Ultra-sound examination, which allows you to identify the tumor at an early stage. Not only young children, no matter how old a person is, he must pass the Ultra-sound examination once a year. In everyday conditions, I recommend reducing salt from the ration in consumption,

not drinking carbonated drinks, lemonades, and not orange-colored fruits. This has a negative effect on the urinary tract system. Currently, prostate adenomas occur in many people to the future doctor we can see ways to eliminate them as follows. There are no preventive methods of prostate adenoma. However, you can prevent prostate cancer. To do this, men over 50 years of age are recommended to perform an appearance and blood analysis at least once a year to a urologist-doctor. Prostate cancer is the second largest cancer in the world in terms of the number of people affected, after lung cancer.

When modern examination tools are used, effective treatment in determining the problem accurately and based on this will help for treatments. Advanced diagnostic tools allow urologist doctors to diagnose diseases in the early stages.

Treatment technologies are also of great importance. urology, especially Pediatric Urology, is a very delicate field that requires high accuracy from doctors. Offers minimally invasive urological operas using new medical technologies. Such operas are more effective and less traumatic, unlike traditional methods.

In such operas, surgical intervention is carried out through several small incisions around one centimeter. Therefore, children practically do not feel pain, they do not have traces of large scars, as in ordinary operas, while the recovery period is significantly reduced, as a result of which children will soon be able to return to their homes. One example is the latest generation technology, the Da Vinci robot. He is making it possible to achieve great success in conducting urological operas in patients. This is a unique technological equipment that performs its most complex operas with maximum accuracy under the management of a surgeon. This robot is much more accurate and faster than the human hand. He can also reach places where doctors cannot get out of the way, where it is most difficult to reach. At the same time, the device reflects an even ten-fold enlarged image of the area under Operation. Operas with his participation are performed in a minimally invasive way.

The teacher must strictly observe a number of conditions, using personally oriented types of education in the learning process.

A feature of personally oriented education is the recognition of the student, the creation of a favorable, necessary environment for his comprehensive development.

- consider each student as a separate person;
- respect the student;
- direct assessment of a student's mental state;
- take into account the wishes, interests of the student;
- tolerant attitude towards each student;
- confidence of the student in strength, opportunities and aspirations;
- creating a favorable educational environment so that each student can sufficiently master the basics of educational disciplines;
- creating an opportunity for free employment of students in independent or subgroups;
- train students to independently monitor their activities, determine the effectiveness of activities, analyze achievement factors and consequences of mistakes;
- exert pressure on each student in the course of study;
- do not identify the shortcomings of an individual student;
- if the student records the inability to master knowledge, inadequate well-being in the learning process, then without sharp conclusions to identify the causes;

- eliminate on the basis of the identified reasons such cases as inability to master knowledge, inadequate well-being of the student without causing harm to his pride;
- create an "atmosphere of success" for each student in the learning process;
- help every student succeed in learning;
- increasing the student's abilities, promoting his development as a person;
- evaluate not the student's identity, but his specific actions;
- as an educator should gain the respect and trust of every student.

Personally oriented education does not provide for the student's adaptation to the education system, but, on the contrary, the creation of the necessary conditions for his comprehensive development, taking into account individual characteristics, the formation of the person. Education of this kind allows students to independently develop, gain independent knowledge, fully demonstrate their internal capabilities, abilities, create the necessary conditions for increasing cognitive activity.

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In the process of personally oriented training, students will receive a creative, critical approach to mastering educational material, the opportunity to promote new ideas, justify them, defend their opinion, find an effective solution in problem situations, master knowledge, skills, skills. The teacher's use in the educational process of various active methods of an innovative nature contributes to the development of students, the further development of their abilities. In particular:

- problem search;
- conducting small studies;
- debate;

- discussion;
- heuristic conversation;
- work in subgroups, etc.

When organizing classes, teachers should pay special attention to ensuring that educational information can interest students, based on their knowledge, skills, skills and experience, stimulate them to think, creative approach. Teachers in the process of training conduct:

- effective, targeted use of various forms, methods, means and technologies;
- provide students with the opportunity to independently choose methods when performing educational tasks;
- ensure the student's work in a pair, subgroup and team;
- drawing attention to the design of classes will not only improve the quality of training, increase its effectiveness, but also create favorable conditions for personal development.

It is important that teachers pay attention not only to the informational, but also to the developing nature of training. In addition, one of the important features of learning is the possibility of independent statements by students on the topic under discussion, a problem studied by the topic (although incorrect, but opinion), in any case pushing them to think and think.

Another sign of personally oriented education is the use in the learning process:

- creative tasks;
- tasks that require a creative approach;
- problem situations;
- role-playing and business games;
- discussion, debate;
- competitions in the form of competitions

Uzbekistan and foreign professors regularly conduct seminars and consultations, as well as exchange experience on new methods of diagnosis and treatment of diseases. The high professional level of urologist doctors from Uzbekistan is excellent, but sometimes the necessary technologies are lacking for their accurate diagnosis. In order to bring this direction to the gorge of modern demand, great attention should be paid to the development of the technological base, directing large investments in the purchase of expensive diagnostic and treatment equipment from abroad for urology departments.

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